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Application and validation of SlideforMAP for assessing shallow landslide probability in New Zealand hill country - Supplementary material

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1. Precipitation event

A radar-based precipitation data is used to compute the precipitation event with the highest return period for the time period of 2000-2010. The year 2000 is the first year of the data availability and 2010 is the year of the landslide inventory. A plot with the highest mean precipitation intensity for events of a duration from 1 hour to 24 hours, with their start time and date are given in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1: Intensity duration curves constructed from NIWA-HIRDS4 dataset [1] with return periods of 100, 50, 20 and 10 years. The return period is computed by minimal MSE fit of the NIWA-HIRDS4 dataset with a general function of $I = a * T^b$. Highest hourly interval intensity events over the years 2000-2010, preceding the landslide inventory, are plotted. The legend displays the date and time of their onset. Figure on the left for the Te Whanga area and Figure on the right for Waikoukou. Plotted lines are for the mean of the precipitation. Numbers above indicate the computed return periods of the event.

2. Relationship of precipitation intensity and maximum lateral flow

Our theoretical routing example for a contributing area in the Waikoukou study area. We routed both an actual event and a constant mean precipitation of the event. This is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: A routing example of lateral macropore flow as a response to the March 2005 rainfall event for an example contributing area in the Waikoukou study area. In the lower left and lower middle are the hydrograph and macropore velocity for the actual rainfall event and a constant mean precipitation event respectively. Both a scenario with and without a runoff coefficient is included. For the runoff coefficient we choose RT2, corresponding to slightly delayed runoff in shallow soils. Upper right is a visualization of the contributing area with distance to the outlet [m]. Lower left and middle left is the macropore flow rate at the outlet as a function of time for the actual event and the constant mean precipitation scenario.

In our example, the peak discharge under the constant mean precipitation (Fig. 2 [lower middle]) with a runoff coefficient is higher than that under no runoff conditions. This seems contradictory, but is the resultant of our computation. We assume groundwater holds a constant velocity after infiltration, that is dependent on the infiltration intensity and a constant assumed macropore diameter. This approach enables the concentration of groundwater under different velocities at the outlet.

We applied the same methodology to a subset of the contributing areas in both the Waikoukou and TeWhanga study area and computed the ratio of macropore flow from a mean and an event precipitation. The results are plotted versus the contributing area size, which we expect to be the best and most practical predictor of this ratio in Fig. 3, 4. These figures are for a scenario with no runoff coefficient and a fixed runoff coefficient. The version with a variable runoff coefficient is published in and applied in the main paper. The resolution of the digital elevation model from which the D8 contributing areas are computed is 2 m.

Fig. 3: Ratio between the maximum lateral flow rate derived from an actual event and a constant mean precipitation with no runoff coefficient. The event is the March 2005 rainfall event and contributing areas are from both the Waikoukou and TeWhanga study area. A linear regression is performed to compute the relationship between this ratio and the contributing area size. The Waikoukou intercept and slope are 6.4 and -1.02 respectively. The TeWhanga intercept and slope are 7.0 and -1.05 respectively.

Fig. 4: Ratio between the maximum lateral flow rate derived from an actual event and a constant mean precipitation with a runoff coefficient of Runoff Type 2. The event is the March 2005 rainfall event and contributing areas are from both the Waikoukou and TeWhanga study area. A linear regression is performed to compute the relationship between this ratio and the contributing area size. The Waikoukou intercept and slope are 5.7 and -0.83 respectively. The TeWhanga intercept and slope are 6.3 and -0.97 respectively.

3. Calibration and validation

The robustness of the calibration and validation method was tested by repeating the method 5 times for the Waikoukou study area with the original version of SlideforMAP as presented in this paper. This is limited for computational reasons. The resulting parameter values and output metrics are given in Fig. 5. Dotty plots displaying parameter narrowing for the best performing of the 5 calibration test runs are given in Fig. 6 to 9.

Fig. 5: Development of the calibration and validation process. The upper four graphs show the resulting value of one of the calibration variables. The lower three graphs give result variables with a blue dot for the calibration value and a red dot for validation values.

Fig. 6: Dotty plots for the repeated calibration and validation process. The plot gives the parameter values of the mean soil thickness versus the resulting AUC for the three calibration rounds.

Fig. 7: Dotty plots for the repeated calibration and validation process. The plot gives the parameter values of the mean saturated soil cohesion versus the resulting AUC for the three calibration rounds.

Fig. 8: Dotty plots for the repeated calibration and validation process. The plot gives the parameter values of the mean friction angle versus the resulting AUC for the three calibration rounds.

Fig. 9: Dotty plots for the repeated calibration and validation process. The plot gives the parameter values of the saturated hydraulic conductivity versus the resulting AUC for the three calibration rounds.

4. Pore water pressure

Fig. 10: Calibrated pore water pressure in Waikoukou. Upper row, mean pore water pressure [kPa] from SfM, SfM org. with SfM parametrization, SfM org., with unique calibration and SfM no hybrid; Lower row list the absolute difference in pore water pressure of the versions as compared to SfM.

5. references

References

[1] Carey-Smith, T., Henderson, R., and Singh, S. (2018). High Intensity Rainfall Design System - Version 4. NIWA Client Report 2018022CH, (August).